

Plasma Technology The beating heart of the technology for modern life in the future

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Abstract

"Plasma" is an ionized gas full of charged and neutral particles that is generally quasi-neutral. Plasma is the fourth state of matter after the three states of solid, liquid and gas. Fire, sun and lightning are examples of plasma found in nature. Scientists consider plasma to be the fourth state of matter because it is something beyond gas. When enough energy enters the gas, it ionizes, that gas changes from an insulator to a conductor, which means it has a combination of reactive species that can have antimicrobial properties. Plasma technology is currently used in commercial markets in the pharmaceutical industry (plasma argon coagulation), waste disposal, cutting and functional modification of various material surfaces to increase the adhesion of simple and multi-layer inks. Many of these applications use thermal plasma, but surface applications generally operate non-thermally.

Keyword: Plasma technology, thermal plasma, applications